

ABOUT THE STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF
POLYMER INSULATORS OF THE CONTACT
NETWORK

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Annotation: Insulators are a crucial element of the contact network, and great attention is paid to improving their characteristics — electrical and mechanical strength. The generally recognized advantages of polymer insulators in comparison with traditional porcelain and glass are manufacturability, low weight, compactness, ease of installation and transportation, high mechanical strength, resistance to impact.

Keywords: polymer insulators, railway substations, glass insulators

The article presents the results of comprehensive studies performed by MIIT on the electro physical characteristics of fiberglass rods and bars made of AG-4S, which were used in the developed polymer structures of the contact network. Recommendations are given on the maintenance of fiberglass rods and bars from AG-4S and their engineering support. The issues of mechanical strength of polymer insulators of the contact network are covered quite fully, therefore, in this article the basic principles of calculating their electrical strength are proposed.

The first generation of polymer insulators were devices endowed with a fiberglass rod and a shell applied to it, which was formed by gluing along each edge. Already in the insulators of the second generation, they began to use a solid silicon-organic protective shell, but they continued to seal the device by gluing the entry point of the rod into the end cap. In modern polymer insulators belonging to third-generation devices, a protective shell with a high degree of adhesion is used, which increased the reliability of maintaining its tightness, and therefore increased the service life of the device.

Modern polymer insulators are distinguished by several types:

- traverses for overhead lines with a capacity of 10-220 kV;
- devices in the form of insulating spacers between phases;
- railway insulators of various series;
- supporting linear isolating devices;
- solid-cast suspension insulators.

In the design of such products, the silicone shell of solid casting is often continued to be used. It is also possible to perform with uniform crimping of the rod and with steel end caps that have undergone the hot-dip galvanizing procedure.

Insulating devices in polymer design are endowed with the following advantages:

- Their small weight provides significant financial savings during transportation, when compared with glass or porcelain products.
- They are easy to install, which also reduces the cost of installation work.
- Such insulators are not susceptible to beating during loading and unloading operations and during transportation.
- It is allowed to use such devices in mountains and swampy areas.
- They are resistant to contamination, so there is no need to clean the insulator during the entire service life.
- High resistance to external influences ensures its reliability and durability in operation.
- These are also affordable products, the cost of which is often lower in comparison with models made of porcelain, glass or ceramics.

Insulators of the contact network of electrified railways for fastening wires in insulating suspensions and at railway substations with a voltage of 3 kV DC and a voltage of 25 kV AC in an atmosphere with varying degrees of contamination.

The main elements of polymer insulators of CS RZD are: a rod made of unidirectional fiberglass, a protective polymer shell and metal end caps.

All types of insulators are presented in our catalog: suspended, tension, locking and cantilever.

Contact network insulators are devices for isolating live wires. Insulators are distinguished by the direction of application of loads and the place of installation — suspended, tension, locking and cantilever, by design — plate and rod, by material — glass, porcelain and polymer. Insulators also include insulating elements of sectional insulators, as well as support elements for horn arresters of sectional disconnectors. The main advantage of glass insulators over porcelain insulators is their ability to self—detect, because their damage can be detected visually (the glass is crumbling). Polymer insulators are much stronger, more reliable and lighter than porcelain and glass insulators, but much more expensive.

Suspended insulators — porcelain and glass plate insulators — are usually connected in garlands of 2 on DC lines and 3-5 (depending on air pollution conditions) on AC lines.

Tension insulators are installed in wire anchors, in load-bearing cables above sectional insulators, in fixing cables of flexible crossbars and rigid crossbars.

The locking insulators of the contact network (Fig. 1 and 2) differ from all others in the presence of a cap with an internal thread for fixing the pipe. On alternating current lines, only rod insulators are used, and with direct current, disc insulators are also used. In the latter case, another disc insulator with an earring is included in the main rod of the articulated retainer.

1. Locking plate insulator

Cantilever porcelain rod insulators (fig. 3) are installed in the struts of insulated consoles. These insulators must have increased mechanical strength, because they work on bending. Porcelain rod insulators are usually used in the rods of insulated consoles. In sectional disconnectors and horn arresters, porcelain rod (less often disc-shaped) insulators are used. In sectional insulators on direct current lines, polymer insulating elements are used in the form of rectangular bars made of a press

material, and on alternating current lines - in the form of cylindrical fiberglass rods, which are covered with electrical protective covers made of fluoroplastic pipes.

2. Locking rod insulator

Polymer core insulators with fiberglass cores and fins made of organosilicon elastomer have been developed. They are used as suspension, sectioning and locking devices; they are promising for installation in stimulating structures of the contact network operate under severe, since along with electrical and mechanical loads, they are affected by atmospheric factors such as solar radiation, temperature, high humidity and rain, wind loads, etc. Therefore, materials must be incorporated into the system of insulating structures that would ensure the stability of electrophysical characteristics under prolonged exposure the factors listed above. A characteristic feature of polymer materials is that their properties largely depend on time. The creep of polymer materials is noticeable at normal temperatures and has a significant effect on the stress-strain state of the structure. The change in the properties of the insulating structure materials over time imposes increased requirements for the calculation of various impacts, including short-term high intensity.uts and rods of insulated consoles, in cables of flexible crossbars, etc. In areas of industrial air pollution and in some artificial structures, periodic cleaning (washing) of porcelain insulators using special mobile means is necessary.

During the implementation of the first stage, polymer insulating structures (insulators) are adequate in their construction length to glass and porcelain ones. As the service life is exhausted, the replacement of traditional insulators with polymer ones does not lead to the reconstruction of the contact network devices. This option is the most promising in use on existing electrified lines, its implementation is possible by the forces of operational personnel.

When overhauling power supply devices or building new lines, the second option is promising, when the bearing, fixing and supporting structures of the contact network are made entirely of polymer material, i.e. they simultaneously perform the functions of a "load-bearing structure-insulator".

Given the high technical and economic efficiency of the introduction of polymer insulating structures of contact electrical networks and the need to solve a wide range of scientific and technical problems in their creation, this work should be considered as a solution to a major scientific problem of important national economic importance.

Techniques for conducting short-term tensile, compression and bending tests of fiberglass rods have been developed. The smallest cross-sectional area of the sample has been established, which makes it possible to determine the strength characteristics of the tested material close to the actual one. It is recommended to take samples with a working part diameter of at least 8 mm for testing. This parameter of cylindrical samples is included in the technical specifications for testing these materials. The deformative properties of fiberglass used in the contact network are subject to the theory of linear viscoelasticity. In short-term tests, the ultimate deformation practically does not change, in long-term tests it depends on the level of applied voltage, temperature and type of binder. The coefficients of working conditions and durability, as well as strength and deformation characteristics of fiberglass, which are used in the practice of designing insulating structures of a contact network made of polymer materials, are obtained.

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